

Characteristics Of The Speech Of Children With Mild Dysarthria

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Abstract: *The article describes pathologies of the articulatory apparatus in children with mild dysarthria, the neuropsychological and psycholinguistic development of children's speech and the child's unique activities, the process of formation of speech skills, as well as deficiencies observed in the articulatory and vocal apparatus. and mental abilities.*

Keywords — dysarthria, light, speech skills, motor skills, articulation, voice.

INTRODUCTION.

Children with a mild level of dysarthria are divided into 3 groups in L.V.Lopatina's studies, they can be adjusted to the groups divided by R.Ye.Levina according to the formation of language tools: FNR - underdevelopment of phonetic speech; FFN - underdevelopment of phonetic-phonemic speech; NTR - incomplete development of speech. V.A. Kiselyova's research is devoted to the analysis of the reasons why children cannot learn at school. While studying dysgraphic and dyslexic children, the author found out the pronunciation of non-rough sounds and phonemic hearing deficits in most of them. A joint examination with a neuropathologist and a neuropsychologist confirmed the presence of mild dysarthria. A mild form of dysarthria leads to a lack of phonemic hearing, analysis, and synthesis as a primary defect, and it causes specific errors in reading and writing. According to R.Ye.Levina, speech kinesthesia disorders in movement and morphological injury of the speech organs affect the hearing and perception of all sounds in this language system. This leads to poor development of phonemic perception in children with a mild degree of dysarthria. Unintelligible, unclear speech does not allow for the formation of clear auditory perception and control in these children. This deepens the shortcomings in the pronunciation of sounds, the inability to distinguish between incorrect pronunciation and the pronunciation of others, has stopped the process of "adapting" one's own articulation to a certain acoustic situation. V.A. Kiselyova sheds light on the problem of correcting and diagnosing the mild form of dysarthria in preschool age in order to prevent written speech disorders in children and to warn them of not being able to master it at school.

Acquiring the correct pronunciation of sounds develops on the basis of the close connection of sensory and motor functions, which ensure the unity of the speech system. On the one hand, the correct acquisition of the sound side of speech determines the development of the phonemic and perceptive level of perception in many ways. On the other hand, during the development of speech, the auditory analyzer feels the influence of the speech movement analyzer: the child hears and perceives the sounds as he pronounces them, and the child hears the sounds he pronounces correctly, or vice versa. Also, in order for the child to correctly form the sound aspect of

speech, not only the articulatory apparatus should be ready for this, but also he should be able to hear well and have the ability to differentiate between his own and others' speech. In the mild form of dysarthria, the disturbance of the formation of phonemic hearing in children is secondary in nature. This type of defect occurs in pathological speech kinesthesias, injuries in the motor organs of the speech organs, phonemic hearing disorders of a secondary nature, the level of expression of which depends on the level of expression of dysarthria itself. Children are bad at distinguishing close sounds (on the basis of pictures), choosing pictures for the given sounds, and making familiar things in syllables.

In children with a mild level of dysarthria, the motility of articulatory organs is disturbed due to pathologies of the articulatory apparatus (hypertonus, hypotonus, deviation, hypertinesis, hypersolivation, etc.), articulatory movements deteriorate. This motor deficiency has a negative effect on the formation of phonemic hearing. These disorders resist the acquisition of mental operations that make up phonemic perception. Due to this, the phonemic skills, skills and imaginations that perform phonemic analysis in the mental framework (qualification) are not formed. Also, a violation of the communication between the hearing and speech movement apparatus leads to the inability to adequately master the sound content of the word, which, in turn, is reflected in the process of learning to read and write.

Impaired clarity of articulation during speech, unintelligible speech of children with a mild level of dysarthria does not allow the formation of clear auditory perception. Children often cannot control their pronunciation. Disturbance of kinesthetic control and auditory differentiation is the cause of persistent disorder of prosodic and phonemic aspects of speech. Inability to distinguish non-speech sounds indicates an underdeveloped state of auditory attention. Almost all children with problems distinguishing non-speech sounds have adenoid tumors in the otolaryngological report (II stage).

Children are better able to distinguish the sounds they are familiar with, which are often encountered in life and during training, than the sounds they are hearing for the first time and which are not familiar to them. Many children are found to be deficient in both rhythmic perception and repetition of rhythmic lines when tested. Some tasks were completed after two or even three attempts due to the lack of attention span. In

this case, motor disorders are clearly visible. Some children cannot complete these tasks, they refuse to complete the tasks. Children with dysarthria have non-uniform vowels when they are tested to distinguish between similar sound complexes and similar words based on sound content. reflects uhs. Deficiency is observed in everyone, but expressed in different degrees. Many children independently correct tasks completed with mistakes.

Often, children do not notice their mistakes. Children perform the tasks of differentiating and separating close words according to their sound content with difficulty. Applause is required in such assignments. If the speech therapist mispronounces a word out of many words, the child claps. (wire - pants, rice - rice). All children have difficulties in distinguishing syllables and phonemes, only after several attempts (two, three, four) children can distinguish a given vowel sound from a row of other vowels. All children have deficiencies in differentiating syllables with oppositional consonants: syllables with voiced and unvoiced sounds.

Difficulties are observed not only in distinguishing sounds that differ according to subtle acoustic-articulatory signs, but also in specific sounds. In some children with dysarthria, the main difficulty is in repeating the chain of bugs. Specific distortions are reflected in matching the second bug in to the first, in changing the place of bugs in the chain of bugs. Many scientists suggest the formation of children's phonemic hearing in order to successfully eliminate phonetic, lexical-grammatical disorders, prevent dysgraphia and dyslexia. In addition, good phonemic hearing helps children distinguish prosodic aspects in the speech of others and allows them to successfully overcome prosody deficits.

In dysarthria, there may be defects in the tone of the pronunciation of sounds:

- severity of pronunciation disorders, specific difficulty in overcoming them;

- specific difficulties in automatizing sounds (automation process takes more time compared to dyslalia). If speech therapy training is not completed on time, acquired speech skills will be forgotten;

- not only consonants, but also the pronunciation of vowel sounds.

- increased mispronunciation of sounds s, z, sh, j, ch, which are pronounced between the teeth and near the tongue; unvoiced pronunciation of voiced consonants (insufficient participation of the voice in the pronunciation of voiced sounds); - soft pronunciation of hard consonants (palatalization);

- special manifestation of sound pronunciation disorder during speech. It is especially observed when the volume of speech increases, in some cases the general uncertainty of speech increases. Depending on the type of disorder, all dysarthria disorders are divided into two categories: anthropophonic (incorrect interpretation of sounds) and phonological (substitution, mixing). Dysarthria speech

disorder is the most common case of sound slippage during speech.

Speech breathing disorders. Breathing disorders in children with dysarthria are associated with insufficient central respiratory regulation. The depth of breathing will not be sufficient. The rhythm of breathing is disturbed, the speech accelerates during expression. Violation of breathing and exhalation coordination is observed (increased inhalation and reduced shallow exhalation). Exhalation occurs mainly through the nose, despite the fact that the mouth is half open. Breathing disorders are especially manifested in the hyperkinetic form of dysarthria.

Voice disorder. Voice disorders are caused by changes in muscle tone and restriction of movement of the tongue and lips, vocal cords, soft palate, and larynx muscles. In most cases, it is noted that the voice is insufficient (unsound, hoarse, rasping, interrupted, excited, throaty). In various forms of dysarthria, voice disorders have a specific character.

Disruption of expressiveness, melodiousness and tempo-rhythmic characteristics of speech. Disturbance of tone and expressiveness of speech is one of the main symptoms of dysarthria. It is these that affect the intelligibility, emotionality and expressiveness of speech at a high level. There is very little expressiveness or the absence of voice modulations (the child cannot voluntarily change the pitch of the voice). The child's voice becomes monotonous and unmodulated. Disturbance of the tempo of speech is manifested by the slowing down of speech, and in rare cases by its acceleration. In some cases, there is a violation of the tone of speech (for example, in the expression of speech by increasing additional accents in words).

Insufficiency of kinesthetic sensations in the articulatory apparatus. In children with dysarthria, not only the limitation of the volume of articulatory movements, but also the weakness of kinesthetic senses of the position and movement of articulatory movements are noted.

Vegetative disorders. One of the most common autonomic disturbances in dysarthria is hypersalivation. Strong drooling is associated with limited movement of the tongue muscles, impaired voluntary swallowing, paresis of the lip muscles. Hypersalivation is usually aggravated by the weakness of kinesthetic sensations in the articulatory apparatus (the child does not feel that saliva is flowing) and the weakening of self-control. Hypersalivation can be expressed at different levels. It is permanent or in certain conditions, it can be observed. Even the mildest case of hypersalivation (moistening of the corners of the lips during speech, a small amount of saliva) indicates the presence of neurological symptoms in the child. Vegetative disorders such as reddening or whitening of the skin on the outside, strong sweating during speech expression are rare.

Violation of the act of eating. In children with dysarthria, the act of eating is often difficult, and in severe cases, there is no movement of chewing solid food, breaking off a bite and biting. In the process of swallowing, choking and wheezing are often noted. Difficulty drinking from a cup. In some cases, breathing and swallowing coordination is disturbed.

The presence of synkinesias. Synkinesias are the simultaneous execution of involuntary movements during the performance of voluntary articulatory movements (for example, raising the lower jaw and the lower lip when raising the tip of the tongue). Oral synkinesis is the opening of the mouth during any movement or attempt to move. Increased laryngeal (return) reflex.

Violation of coordination of movements (ataxia). The state of ataxia appears in dysmetric, asynergic and noisy states of the speech tone. Dysmetria is defined as inconsistency and inaccuracy of voluntary articulatory movements. The condition of dysmetria is usually expressed in the form of hypermetria. In this case, the necessary movements are performed excessively in relation to the desired state, rudely, at a slower pace (excessive increase of the movement amplitude). In some cases, there is a violation of coordination (imbalance) between breathing, voice production and articulation. Ataxia is noted in ataxic dysarthria. Presence of compulsive movements (hyperkinesis and tremors) in articular muscles. Hyperkinesis - involuntary, involuntary, forced movements of body muscles and facial muscles (hyperkinetic dysarthria). Tremor is a trembling of the tip of the tongue (it is very noticeable in precisely directed movements). Tongue tremor occurs in ataxic dysarthria.

Levels of manifestation of dysarthria Levels of manifestation of dysarthria depend on the degree and nature of damage to the central nervous system. The levels of manifestation of dysarthria are conditionally divided into 3 levels:

- Light;
- Medium;
- Heavy.

A mild degree of dysarthria is characterized by minor disturbances in the structure of the defect (speech and non-speech symptoms). A milder manifestation of dysarthria is usually referred to as "non-severe" or "mild" dysarthria. This includes paresis of the muscles of the articulatory apparatus, which disrupts the process of sound pronunciation. In some cases, practicing speech therapists use the terms "minimal dysarthric disorder", "dysarthric component", and in these cases, some of them bee wrongly consider these phenomena as deviation disorders between dyslalia and dysarthria. At a mild level of dysarthria, the general intelligibility of speech may not be impaired, but the pronunciation of sounds is somewhat mixed and unclear. Misinterpretation is observed when pronouncing sonorous and noisy sounds. The most difficult vowel sounds are "i" and "u". In most cases, voiced consonants are voiceless. In some cases (especially when a speech therapist works), the child can pronounce sounds correctly in isolated cases, but with an increase in the volume of speech, it is possible to note the overall unclear state of the pronunciation of sounds. Insufficient speech breathing (accelerated, not very deep), insufficient voice (low, dull) is also observed. In the mild level of dysarthria, a non-sharp violation of the tone of the tongue muscles is observed in children. In some cases, an insignificant decrease in the articulatory movement of the lips

is observed. In these cases, subtle and differentiated movements at the tip of the tongue are disturbed (first of all, lifting the tongue up). Non-verbal symptoms may also appear, chewing hard food, slight grunting during swallowing, increased swallowing reflex is observed. In the middle level of dysarthria, the overall intelligibility of speech is disturbed. The speech becomes unintelligible to others. In some cases, it is difficult to understand a child's speech if you do not know the content of the text. In children, when pronouncing sounds, a common mixed sound is produced. Sometimes the sounds at the end of the word and paired consonants are omitted. Violation of the depth and rhythm of breathing is accompanied by a violation of voice timbre and strength. The lack of voice modulation makes the child's speech monotonous. In children, the tone of the tongue, lips and facial muscles is impaired. Their faces are hypomimic, the articulatory movements of the tongue and lips are slowed down, strictly limited, not clear. Difficulty keeping the language in a certain state and changing from one state to another. The phenomenon of hypersalivation, difficulty in the act of eating, synkinesia, and the strengthening of the vomiting reflex are considered characteristic for children with a moderate level of dysarthria. In the severe level of dysarthria - anarthria - complete paralysis of speech movement muscles or the inability to pronounce sounds at all is considered. Anarthria is caused by a severe injury (injury) of the central nervous system. Similar defects occur in language motor skills. The type of dysarthric speech disorder is determined depending on the nature of its clinical syndrome.

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